

Measures for Promoting Emotional Intelligence of Teachers in Government Technical Colleges for Improving Performance in Enugu State

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Abstract

The main purpose of the study was to determine the measures for promoting emotional intelligence of teachers in Government Technical Colleges for Improved performance in Enugu State. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses. A survey design was adopted for the study. The population used for the study was 38 technical college teachers in two Government technical colleges in Enugu State (GTC Enugu and GTC Nsukka) offering vocational trades programme in the State. There was no sampling due to the manageable size of the population. The instrument used for data collection was a 21-item structured questionnaire grouped into two sections according to the research questions that guided the study. The items were structured in four-point rating scale. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from Department of Technology and Vocational Education and one who majored in Measurement and Evaluation from Department of Mathematics and Computer Science Education, all from Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha which yielded 0.83. Out of 38 copies of questionnaire distributed, 34 copies were returned giving 89.47% return rate. Mean with standard deviation which t-test statistical tools was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.5 level of significance used to answer the research questions. Based on the data analysed, the study identified government and institution administrative measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State. Based on the findings of the study recommendations were made, among others include: government should organize or sponsor workshops and seminars in technical colleges to promote technical teachers' emotional intelligence, school administrators should provide the needed environment that would promote technical teachers' emotional intelligence in their guidance services.

Keywords Government Technical College; Emotional Intelligence; Improved Performance

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Introduction

Education has gained such an unpredicted prominence in the world that both developed and developing countries strive to provide quality education for the overall development of the citizenry. Education has become the key to the overall development of human life. Onyebuanyi, Mbah and Odeluga (2017) opined that education is the medium of acquisition of minimum ethical standards that can propel its recipient towards the development of oneself and nation at large. It is the foundation upon which all aspects of development rest and no nation can develop more than the quality of education its environment can provide (Federal Republic of Nigeria FRN, 2013). Therefore, the training of students in Technical College Education is not only aimed at producing outstanding intellectual human capacity but also emotionally and spiritually healthy ones that can contribute to the well-being and progress of the nation. The implication is that emotional development and management are prioritized in the development of students irrespective of course or discipline. Ekwesianya and Orji (2017) pointed that emotional development of students in schools are prerogative though neglected by the teachers.

Vocational guiding services is an assistance given to an individual in solving the problems that are related to occupational choice, progress of the study, individual characteristics and related occupational opportunity. According to Thenmozhi (2018) vocational guidance is the process of assisting the individual to choose an occupation, prepare for it, enter upon and progress in it. Teachers in technical colleges are required to teach and also provide vocational services to the students in order to choose wisely in developing life goals, in making adjustment and in solving problems that confront them in the attainment of their goal. The teachers are required to be emotionally intelligent in order to provide placement services that enable the students to discover information about themselves, his/her abilities, interests, needs, ambitions, limitations and their causes. Technical college teachers are required to provide guidance that will help individual students through his efforts, discover and develop his potentials for his personal happiness and social usefulness. This is equally pertinent in the present society where students are under the influence of “get rich quick syndrome” instead of acquiring vocational skills provided to them at the technical colleges.

Technical colleges are post primary education programme designed to train craftsmen and master craftsmen in different vocational/career and technical skill areas. Mbah (2016) and Okolie, Igwe and Elom (2019) stated that technical college programmes are aimed at training intermediate workforce with relevant skills for employment in facilities like machine, electrical, electronic control techniques and materials. Technical colleges are vocational training institutions which expose the students to technical education programme with the objective of producing craftsmen and master craftsmen that can use tools and materials properly in production and service setting.

Further, technical colleges in Enugu State are designed to develop abilities, understanding, work habits and appreciation, encompassing knowledge, skills and information needed by workers to enter and make progress in employment on a useful and productive basis. At this technical college level, occupational-specific education is provided to students through technical education instructional approaches. The curriculum of technical colleges (TCs) focus on crafts, engineering trades and technical skills (Okolie, Igwe and Elom, 2019.) The use of emerging technologies for its implementation and to achieve the desired objectives in the learners are required. The application of emotional intelligence in trade subjects would facilitate capacity building of competent craftsmen and master craftsmen from technical colleges. Amongst the trades offered to students in Nigeria TCs include bricklaying, carpentry, plumbing, painting, motor vehicle repair and maintenance, air condition and refrigeration, radio and television maintenance, machining, welding and fabrication and home economics. The trades are properly planned to equip learners to understand skills for paid and self-employment in a specific area. Poor implementation of vocational guidance in technical colleges programmes according to Mbah and Elobuikwe (2016) have hindered the psychological, emotional, socio-political, technological and economic development of the students in their chosen occupational field.

In recent times, technical colleges like other educational institutions are facing a daunting task of providing vocational and occupational guidance to the students and some of the teachers are not emotionally intelligent on addressing the vocational needs of the students. It is imperative to note that irrespective of level of education and training, technical college students are expected to be academically, socially and emotionally sound on task in the field of work.

Emotion can be seen as a sort of feeling or effective experiences which are characterized by some psychological cognitive and situational factors. According to Ugoni (2015) emotions affect relationship between people, self-identity and ability to complete a task. Human emotion determines individual attitude to love, defences and protection of values, mourning at loss and overcoming difficult obstacles in pursuit of achievable goals. It is important to state that emotion is the primary source of human energy, aspirations and drive, activation of innermost and purpose of life and transforming them from things to value of life. The concept of emotional intelligence was coined by Peter Salovey and John Mayer in 1990. It is usually measured by Emotional Intelligence Quotient (EQ). Ekwesianya and Orji (2017), pointed out that emotional intelligence describes ability, capacity, skill or a self-perceived ability to assess, identify and manage the emotions of one's self, of others and of group. Understanding individual emotional intelligence helps the individual in making self-judgment, reactions and decision making to accept or reject as condition demands.

Emotional intelligence has two major domains as contained in the Mixed Model of emotional Intelligence by Goleman (1995). They are self – awareness and self-motivation. Self-awareness of an individual is the ability to realize and know one's own feeling in situation and be able to choose a priority in making decision and actions (Ugoani and Ewuzie, 2013). The authors further explained that self-motivation refers to the ability of an individual to striving or meet a standard of excellence. Therefore, self—motivation helps people to maintain initiative and perseverance to improve capabilities to address challenges and obstacle in life and tend towards improving excellent performance. Technical teachers as trainers need to develop their emotional intelligence through the self-awareness and self-motivation. Hassan and Halil (2013) stated that, teachers need to develop the consciousness and capacity towards managing their emotion and that of students in every situation. Becoming emotionally intelligent is imperative in teaching and learning.

Without consideration to the level of training and qualification possessed by the teachers, there is need to identify measures that would improve the technical teachers' emotional intelligence. Alio (2021) pointed that stakeholders in education like government, school administrators, parents and non-governmental organizations need to develop practical and acceptable approaches in reawakening the teachers' emotional intelligence to students learning. Government as an authoritative institution has a role to play in training and retraining of technical teachers to improve their emotional intelligence. This could be done by providing enabling environment, organizing workshops and seminars to inculcate the habit and interest of becoming emotionally intelligent in their job performance. Also, the school administrators need to promote the technical teachers' self-awareness and self-motivation in controlling the students' activities irrespective gender, personal emotion and conditions.

A technical teacher may be male or female as both genders need to develop positive attitude and be emotionally intelligent in handling students' vocational issues. Through provision of supportive services to manage emotional stress, retraining staff and development of sustainable framework and policy for staff welfare growth would be enhance (Arum, 2016). Adopting and implementing these measures would improve the technical teachers' emotional intelligence in technical colleges.

This is necessitated from the findings of Adigwe (2015) and Shrestha (2015) that emotional intelligence has significant influence on students' performance in their overall development therefore measure to promote the technical teacher's emotional intelligence are needed in the technical colleges. Identifying these would assist the educational system to improve the quality of services provided as the students in technical colleges need to prepare adequately by the technical teachers for vocational career development the technical teachers need to teach their students as well as assist them in developing their emotional capabilities for vocational and social inclusiveness. It is against this background that the need arose to determine the measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

The training of students in technical colleges is dependent on the teachers who ought to provide academic, psychological, emotional and vocational guidance for the students. The provision of this type of balanced of education is to equip the students with the consciousness to relate with other people, technologies and social life. Research findings by Adigwe (2015) and Shrestha (2015) revealed that lack of emotional intelligence attributes among the teachers has led to teachers' negligence in other areas of students' learning and vocational development

but concentrated on academic learning. This negligence has increased the level of indiscipline, cultism and other immoral social life that are against the values and norms of human life.

Technical college students in their vocational areas are not exceptional as they equally face the same negligence. It is important to note that the training of students in technical colleges is not only for academic performance but to inculcate moral values, emotional and psychological training to leave a successful life. The researcher is worried on the poor attention given by technical teachers on the emotional and psychological development of students which may negatively influence their normal academic exercise. Ekwesianya and Orji (2017) pointed that teachers have not made significant achievement in managing their emotions in the performances of their duties and this could be seen in the quality of vocational guidance that they provide to the students in technical colleges. Therefore, the teachers need to be encouraged in other areas of their pedagogical qualities (including being emotionally intelligent) which will improve their service delivery. The problem of this study put in question form is; what are the measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State?

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the measures for promoting emotional intelligence of teachers in government technical colleges in Enugu State.

Specifically, the study sought to determine the:

1. The government related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of teachers in government technical colleges in Enugu State.
2. The school administrative related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of teachers in government technical colleges in Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What are the government related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of teachers in government technical colleges in Enugu State.
2. What are the school administrative related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of teachers in government technical colleges in Enugu State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. H_{01} : There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers in technical colleges on the government related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of teachers in government technical colleges in Enugu State.
2. H_{02} : There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers in technical colleges on the school administrative related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of teachers in government technical colleges in Enugu State.

Method

This study adopted a survey research design. According to Nworgu (2015) survey research design is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few of them to represent the entire group. This design was adopted due to the responses from sample of technical college teachers used for the study could be generalized to the rest of other technical teachers in technical colleges in Enugu State of Nigeria. Enugu State is one of the five States in Southeast Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. The population comprised 38 teachers from two Government Technical Colleges in Enugu State (GTC Enugu and GTC Nsukka). The population was determined from the preliminary survey conducted by the researcher. The number was manageable and as such, there was no sampling.

The data collection was carried out using 21 item structured questionnaire developed by the researcher based on the related literature. The instrument was structured in four-point response option of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from Department of Technology and Vocational Education and one who majored in Measurement and Evaluation, Department of Mathematics and Computer Education all from Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu. The corrections and suggestions of the experts after the validation were used to produce the final instrument used for the study. The instrument was trial tested using 20 technical teachers in GTC Umunze and Umuchu in Anambra State which were not part of the population under study. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability index. It yielded .83 reliability index. This .83 coefficient is in-line with Uzoagulu (2011) that reliability index of .60 to 1 show that the instrument is highly reliable.

Two research assistants were used in the administration of the questionnaire and out of 38 copies distributed 34 copies were returned giving 89.47% return rate. Weighted means and standard deviations were used to answer the research questions. Decisions on the research questions were made using the lower and upper limits of the mean based on a four-point rating scale. The standard deviation was used to determine the homogeneity or otherwise of the opinions of the respondents. The t- test was used to test the null hypotheses. The analysis was carried out using Statistical Packages Social Science (SPSS). The significant value (at 2-tail) was compared with .05 level of significant at the appropriate degree of freedom. The null hypothesis was not rejected where the significant value was less than the .05 level of significance and at appropriate degree of freedom; otherwise, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Results

The results of the study are presented according to the research questions and hypotheses that guided the study.

Research Question 1

What are the government related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of teachers in government technical colleges in Enugu State?

Table 1: Respondents’ mean scores on the government related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of teachers in government technical colleges in Enugu State

S/N	The government related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teacher includes to:	Male N = 21		Female N= 13		Overall		Decision
		X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂	X _G	SD _G	
1	Organising in-service training for technical teachers on emotional intelligence	3.52	0.56	3.56	0.55	3.54	0.55	Strongly Agree
2	Providing motivational package apart from salaries	3.15	0.74	3.16	0.73	3.15	0.73	Agree
3	Providing stress control avenues to manage physical stress	2.98	0.75	2.96	0.75	2.97	0.75	Agree
4	Providing stress control facilities to manage emotional stress	2.99	0.77	2.99	0.76	2.99	0.77	Agree
5	Providing technical teachers with vacation for multidimensional experience	3.00	0.62	3.02	0.61	3.01	0.62	Agree
6	Improving security of technical teachers in the institutions	3.05	0.58	3.04	0.59	3.05	0.58	Agree
7	Providing effective communication channel between the government and staff	3.24	0.76	3.23	0.76	3.23	0.76	Agree
8	Providing excellent standard in school for self-motivation	2.95	0.85	2.95	0.86	2.95	0.85	Agree
9	Providing conducive job environment for teacher-student interaction	3.01	0.79	3.06	0.78	3.30	0.79	Agree
10	Enforcing social life activities to promote social intelligence	2.92	0.79	3.06	0.78	3.30	0.79	Agree
11	Providing monitoring on the implementation of emotional intelligence in the institution	3.19	0.61	3.20	0.60	3.19	0.61	Agree
	Cluster Mean /SD	3.90	0.64	3.10	0.71	3.90	0.71	Agree

Note: X = Mean; SD =Standard Deviation

The analysis of data presented in **Table 1** showed that the overall mean score for item 1 is

3.54 indicating strongly agree. The remaining 10 items mean scores range from 2.92 to 3.23 showing agree. This means that the items were the government related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State, The overall cluster mean of 3.09 further showed agree. The cluster shows low standard deviation of .71 indicates that the respondents have relatively similar opinion on itemized measures.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female teachers on the measures related for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State.

Table 2:
Summary of t-test analysis of mean scores of male and female technical college teachers on the measures related for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State

Variables	N	T	df	Sig (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	21	0.167	32	0.817	0.14423	0.86312	NS
Female	13						

NS: Not Significant

The result of t-test analysis in **Table 2** shows that the t-value at .05 level of significance and 32 degrees of freedom for the 11 items is .167 with a significant value of .817. Since the significant value of .817 is more than the .05 level of significance the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female technical college teachers on government related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State.

Research Question 2

What are the school administrative related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State?

Table 3:
Mean ratings and standard deviation on the school administrative related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State

S/N	The school administrative related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of teachers include:	Male N = 21		Female N = 13		Overall		Decision
		X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂	X _G	SD _G	
12	Conducting emotional intelligence workshop for technical teachers	3.33	0.65	3.34	0.66	3.34	0.65	Agree
13	Retraining the teachers on strategies to manage emotional intelligence challenges	2.97	0.81	2.97	0.81	2.97	0.81	Agree
14	Sympathizing with staff when passing through trial times	3.31	0.79	3.09	0.79	3.20	0.79	Agree
15	Given needed compensation to technical teacher in their job performance	2.97	0.76	2.96	0.77	2.97	0.77	Agree
16	Organizing training for staff on the consciousness of being emotionally intelligent	3.01	0.76	2.99	0.76	3.00	0.76	Agree
17	Opening a functional communication channel to interact with staff	3.08	0.75	3.22	0.76	3.20	0.75	Agree
18	Encouraging the technical teacher to enjoy job vacation	3.02	0.76	3.01	0.77	3.02	0.76	Agree
19	Improving security of technical teacher in institution of learning	3.07	0.73	3.09	0.73	3.08	0.73	Agree
20	Maintaining favourable policy in the school for teachers' job	3.03	0.71	3.03	0.72	3.03	0.71	Agree
21	Development of an equitable emotional condition for staff development	3.14	0.57	3.16	0.55	3.16	0.56	Agree
	Cluster Mean /SD	3.90	0.73	3.09	0.73	3.10	0.73	Agree

Note: X = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation

The data presented in **Table 3** above indicates that the overall item mean ratings range from 2.97 to 3.34 depicting agree. This shows that the respondents agree to the items as the school administrative measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State. The overall cluster mean score of 3.10 indicates agree. The low standard deviation of .73 shows that the respondent's opinions are homogeneous to the items as school administrative related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in vocational guidance in Enugu State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female technical college teachers on the school administrative measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State.

Table 4:
Summary of t-test analysis of mean ratings of male and female technical college teachers on the school administrative measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in vocational guidance in Enugu State

Variables	N	T	Df	Sig (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	21	0.029	32	0.972	0.08513	0.89869	NS
Female	13						

NS: Not Significant

The result of t-test analysis in **Table 4** above shows that the t-value at .05 level of significance and 32 degree of freedom for the items is 0.029 with a significant value of .972. As the significant value of 0.972 is more than the 0.05 level of significance the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference with respect to the items on the mean scores of male and female technical college teachers on the school administrative related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State.

Summary of Findings of the Study

Based on the results of data analysis, the following findings were made:

1. There are numerous government measures for promoting emotional intelligence among teachers and this was signified by the grand mean of 3.09. There was also not significant difference in the mean response of male and female teachers.
2. No significant difference in the mean response of male and female teachers, it was revealed that school administrative measures of promoting emotional intelligence was prevalent in schools

Discussion

The findings of the study according to research question one showed identified government related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State. The government related measures for promoting technical college teachers' emotional intelligence include; government should organize in-service training for technical college teachers on emotional intelligence, providing motivational packages apart from salaries, stress control avenues to manage physical stress, stress control facilities to manage emotional stress, technical college teachers with vacation for multidimensional experience. Improving security of technical college teachers in the institutions, providing effective communication channel between the government and staff, providing excellent standard in school for self-motivation, providing excellent standard in school for self-motivation. Providing conducive job environment for student interaction, enforcing social life activities to promote social intelligence and providing monitoring on the implementation of emotional intelligence in the institution. The study indicated that government can improve the emotional intelligence of technical college teachers through these measures. The findings of the study agreed with those of Ekwesianya and Orji (2017) that government need to organize workshops and seminars for the technical college teachers to improve their job performance in vocational

guidance. This could equally be achieved through the provision of facilities and platforms that would reduce emotional stress in the job performance of technical college teachers.

Further, the findings of the study indicated that there was no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female technical college teachers on the government related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State. This showed that emotional intelligence is not influenced by gender. This was also in line with Adigwe (2015) who pointed that gender had no significant influence on the job performance of teachers with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Furthermore, the study revealed with respect to the school administrative related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State. The school administrative related measures include: conducting emotional intelligence workshop for technical teachers, retraining the teachers on strategies to manage emotional intelligence challenges, sympathizing with staff when passing through trial times, given needed compensation to technical teachers in their job performance, organizing training for staff on the consciousness of being emotionally intelligent. Opening a functional communication channel to interact with staff encouraging the technical college teachers to enjoy job vacation, improving security of technical college teachers in institution of learning. Maintaining favourable policy in the institution for lecturer's job and developing an equitable emotional condition for staff development. The findings of the study showed that school administration has measures to adopt in promoting the teachers' emotional intelligence in technical college. The findings of the study were in consonance with Alio (2021) that the school administrators should provide the teachers with in-service programmes and enabling environment to understand their emotional intelligence and work towards managing it or improved job performance through proper vocational guidance. The school administration according to the findings may develop a welfare package to promote the emotional intelligence of the technical college teachers for improve in Enugu State technical colleges.

In a related development, the findings of the study showed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female technical college teachers on the school administrative measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State. The implication of the findings was that gender of the respondents had no significant influence on the identified school administrative measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu State.

Conclusion

Technical college teachers' job performance in colleges is primary for the achievement of the technical college objectives in training craftsmen and master craftsmen for sustainable livelihood. In achieving these objectives, their emotional intelligence on the job needs to be properly considered for quality job performance is dependent on individual emotional state. The study examined the measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in vocational guidance. Based on the findings of the study, the study concluded that all the identified items under the government and school administrative related measures are relevant for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in their services to the students. Also, there was no significant influence of gender on the identified government and school administrative related measures for promoting emotional intelligence of technical college teachers in Enugu state.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Government should organize or sponsor workshops and seminars in technical colleges on promoting technical teachers' emotional intelligence in Enugu State.
2. Government should provide platforms that would enable technical college teachers to improve their emotional intelligence in Enugu State.
3. School administrators should provide the teachers with the needed environment that would promote their emotional intelligence in technical colleges in Enugu State.

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